

Research Article

**Family support and self-care in the management of diabetes patients’
perspectives from Pettah region of Indian state of Kerala**

***Radhakrishnan V., Parvathi M.,
Dinesh Kajoriya and R K Mishra**

Department of General Medicine,
Divisional Railway Hospital Pettah, Kerala India

Article Info:

***Corresponding author:**

Department of General
Medicine, Divisional Railway
Hospital Pettah, Kerala India

*radhakvv@gmail.com

Received:-12-09-2024

Accepted:-25-10-2024

Published:-30-10-2024

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14012713

Abstract

Patients with type 2 diabetes were recruited using convenience sampling. Inclusion criteria included being above the age of 30, having Type 2 Diabetes and being willing to be interviewed/recorded on hospital wards. Patients with other forms of diabetes, pregnancy, and cognitive impairments such as dementia, as well as inability to speak Marathi, Hindi, or English, were excluded. Twenty eligible patients (18.01%) accepted to participate. Men made up 70% of the research participants, women 30%; 60% of the participants were between the ages of 41 and 50; 85% of the participants were married; and 50% of the participants had finished lower secondary and secondary school (grades 11 and 12). Of the patients, the majority (55%) lived in joint family. The involvement of family in daily life routines significantly enhances the management of chronic conditions. As a result, self-care behaviors such as dietary management, exercise, medication are eventually developed. Participants responded positively about their family support. Older persons were happy and grateful to receive the family support. Most of the Female participants were unhappy with the support from husband and other family members.

Keywords: type 2 diabetes, family support, dietary management, exercise, Glycated haemoglobin, medication

Introduction

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is the most common form of diabetes and affects more

than 90% of people with diabetes. DM2 is a chronic metabolic disease associated with high blood glucose levels [1]. In addition to genetic

pre-disposition, physical inactivity, obesity, and unhealthy eating habits are significant risk factors for T2DM [2,3]. The prevalence of type 2 diabetes is increasing globally, and health services in many countries are struggling with the morbidity, mortality, and costs associated with the complications of this long-term condition[4]. Diabetes self-management education (DSME) is important as it can reduce the risks of developing diabetes-related complications and improve glycemic control, at least in the short term [5-7]. Previous studies stated, family support is critical for increasing well-being and diabetes self-management [8], as well as promoting family cohesiveness [9]. Family contexts and relationships are not uniform, and this is reflected in the type of support offered by Family Members (FMs) to promote self-management techniques [10,11]. Family disruptive behaviors, such as arguing over diet, physical activity, or medications, are considered as impediments to the patient's successful self-management [12]. Furthermore, family support correlates with better coping, quality of life, and glycemic outcomes [13]. Conversely, absence, reduction, or loss of family support can have negative health effects on the patients [14]. Self-care practices have been linked to improved glucose control and significantly reduced progression and development of diabetic complications [15,16]. Diabetes-related self-care activities include healthy diet, physical activity, self-monitoring of blood glucose levels, and taking prescribed medications on a regular basis [17]. Adherence to the recommended diabetic self-care activities is critical for attaining desired glycemic control and minimizing diabetes-related complications[18, 19]. Despite the recognized clinical advantages of diabetic self-care activities, some studies show low adherence to suggested diabetes-related self-care measures [20-22].

Ethical Approval: This study was approved by the Divisional Railway Hospital Pettah, Kerala India Research Ethics Committee. Informed written consent was obtained from all

study participants after providing them with a verbal and written explanation about the purpose and required procedures of the study. Data access was restricted to study researchers only. The ethics procedures of the study comply with the Declaration of Helsinki.

Methodology

Data Collection and study setting

A qualitative approach was applied in this study. This study was conducted in Divisional Railway Hospital Pettah, Kerala India. Pettah is an urban neighbourhood of Thiruvananthapuram, the capital of the Indian state of Kerala. Patients with type 2 diabetes were recruited using convenience sampling. Inclusion criteria included participant being above the age of 30, having Type 2 Diabetes and being willing to be interviewed/recorded on hospital premises. Patients with other forms of diabetes, pregnancy, and cognitive impairments such as dementia, as well as inability to speak Marathi, Hindi, or English, were excluded. The inclusion criteria were satisfied by one hundred and eleven patients. After describing the study's goal and methodology to the eligible patients, they agreed to an audiorecorded interview at the hospital. Twenty eligible patients (18.01%) accepted to participate. Interviews continued until theme saturation was achieved [23]. Patients living with diabetes were individually interviewed to explore family support and self-care in diabetes management.

Data Analysis:

Following a review of the literature, the recorded semi-structured interviews topics were designed. Important topics of diabetes self-care were discussed, such as diabetic medication practices, blood glucose self-monitoring, healthy eating, physical activity, and the perception of family support among type 2 diabetics. The interviews were conducted in Marathi and/or Hindi, and the transcripts were translated into English. [24] Transcripts were reviewed and an independent

coder and researchers establish an agreement on topic theme and sub-themes. The resulting framework was utilized to assess the patient's needs in medication, self-care, exercise and need of family support. All of us (Authors) examined the transcribed interviews to ensure they were accurate, thorough, and unbiased [25-27]. Data were analyzed using a basic thematic analysis technique [28] to classify the codes throughout the study. In order to succeed in T2DM self-management, it is crucial to assess and investigate the patient's perception of family support. This study aimed to investigate the significance of patient's perceived family support in T2DM self-management. T2DM self-management is independent, individual-based, and influenced by family support.

Results

Participant Characteristics

Table 1 summarizes the demographics of the 20 participants in the interview. Male made up 70% of the research participants, female 30%; 60% of the participants were between the ages of 41 and 50; The average age was 46.6 years, and the majority of participants had completed lower secondary and secondary school. 85% of the participants were married; and 50% of the participants had finished lower secondary and secondary school (grades 11 and 12). Of the patients, Among the patients, 70% had an income of more than 15,000 INR and 55% lived in a joint/extended household. 80% of the patients had diabetes for more than 12 months, and 60% of patients alone utilized oral hypoglycemic medications to control their diabetes, and 80% of patients had the condition for longer than a year. Eighty percent of the patients had hypertension, and seventy percent had uncontrolled fasting blood sugar (mg/dl). Glycated hemoglobin levels were controllable in 70% of the individuals.

Table 1 Basic characteristics and health profiles of study participants (n=20)

Characteristic	Value (%)
Gender	
Male	14 (70)
Female	6 (30)
Age group (years)	
30-40	2 (10)
41-50	12 (60)
More than 50 year	6 (30)
Marital status	
Never married	1 (5)
married	17 (85)
Widowed	2 (10)
Education	
Illiterate (no formal education)	6 (30)
Primary school level (grades 1-10)	2 (10)
Lower secondary and secondary (grades 11-12)	10 (50)
University degree or higher	2 (10)
Income range (monthly; INR)	
<15,000	6 (30)
>15,000	14 (70)
Family type	
Single family	9 (45)

Joint/extended family	11 (55)
Duration of diabetes	
12 months	4 (20)
>12 months	16 (80)
Diabetes treatment	
Oral hypoglycemic agent only	12 (60)
Oral hypoglycemic agent and insulin	1 (5)
Insulin only	7 (35)
Comorbidities	
Hypertension	16 (80)
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	1 (5)
Cardiovascular diseases other than	3 (15)
Fasting blood sugar (mg/dl) ²	
Controlled (≤ 130)	6 (30)
Uncontrolled (>130)	14 (70)
Glycated hemoglobin level	
Controlled ($<7\%$)	6 (30)
Uncontrolled ($\geq 7\%$)	14 (70)

(mg/dl): milligrams per decilitre

Measurement of diabetes self-care behaviors

In terms of self-care practices, 65% of individuals used oral medication, 35% took insulin, 60% engaged in physical exercise, 50% consumed fatty or red meat-based foods, and 20% monitored their blood sugar levels regularly.

Table 2 Diabetes self-care practices of study participants (n= 20 unless stated otherwise)

Self-care behaviors	n=20	Percentage (%)
Medication adherence		
Oral medicine	13	65
Insulin	7	35
Physical activity (Within past 3 months)		
No activity	1	5
Moderately active	7	35
Active	12	60
Dietary behavior (Everyday-Within past 3 months)		
Vegetables and Fruits	9	45
fatty food or red meat	10	50
No sweet items in diet	1	5
Self-monitoring of blood glucose (At least twelve times in 1 Months.)		
Monitored blood glucose level	5	20

Role of Family (P = Patient (Numbered-1 to 20))

Data analysis highlighted themes about the topic of family support. Family members help with food, exercise, and medication collection;

for example, women may aid diabetes patients (husband/father-in-law), while husbands support the diabetic wife/mother.

1. Help in daily life routine: Family engagement in day-to-day activities greatly improves chronic disease treatment. When people managing diabetes or other chronic conditions receive their support, their entire quality of life, mental stability, and health outcomes can all improve.

Patients Responses:

1. "Family member like my brother discuss me with topics I like. My Family members give encouragement, which helps to enhance my work spirits."(P9, P2)
2. "I feel my family members are mature to understand my diabetic situation. Having understanding family members makes me feel less alone and nervous."(P1, P3)
3. "Families provide me with nourishing meals that satisfy my nutritional needs. Family members participate in physical activities on a regular basis to increase the enjoyment and consistency of exercise."(P1, P20)
4. My family monitoring my blood sugar levels, medication schedules, and food compliance. They serve as a reminder for medications, appointments, and appropriate behavior.(P4, P5, P7)
5. "Family members provide prompt assistance and aid in the effective handling of emergencies. My family represents my interests in medical settings and makes sure I get the attention I need."(P9, P15)

2. Medication Administration

1. "Using medication schedules, family members help me arrange medications and make sure that dosages are given correctly and on time. Maintaining a medication diary enables me to monitor compliance and identify any overlooked dosages."(P8, P11)
2. "I get reminders or alerts from family members to take their medication as prescribed. Positive reinforcement motivates me to follow their medication schedule."(P13, P19)

3. Help in diet management

Family support is essential in the diet management of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM). Involving the family member in meal planning helps ensure that dietary preferences are considered while adhering to nutritional guidelines. Two patients shared the experience of family support in diet management, "My family works together to create meal plans as per suggestions from doctor that support well-balanced, nutrient-dense food while also taking my dietary requirements into consideration. When preparing meals at home, family members prioritize using low-GI foods and serving the right quantity."(P18, P17)

4. Self Monitoring the blood glucose

Self monitoring is the best way to keep ourselves fit, like this statement our patients recorded the following statements "Family members includes big brother and small teenagers assist me in getting the sanitiser and sugar level monitoring machine ready for blood glucose testing. Healthy lifestyle choices made by families, such cooking wholesome meals or working out as a group, help lower blood sugar levels."(P1)

Family members frequently inquire about me, particularly during high-risk periods (e.g., right after exercise or right before meals). During hypoglycemic episodes, offering consolation and confidence may help reduce worry. The majority of patients are satisfied with their families' assistance in managing their hypoglycemia.

According to three patients, their wives provided meals and other forms of self-care.

"We did love marriage and have been married more than thirty-five years, and my wife has played a significant role in managing my type 2 diabetes throughout that time. She may significantly enhance my life by providing continuous emotional support, engaging in social functions, movies, park, health-related activities (P4), and nurturing a positive atmosphere around me always. She always makes sure that my food is appropriate as per

suggestions from doctor.(P5, P11). One statement is very motivational for us as a researcher: His wife tells him not to worry when his blood sugar levels rise because this is normal for diabetics.(P5)

Neglect of diabetic wives by their husbands

We observed some of the negative points while this study, three of the female participants mentioned that their husbands didn't provide them much assistance.

“My spouse cannot have take me into consideration in any decisions, not getting me to the doctor for regular checkups, and he always neglect me about my diet and medications, no emotional and motivational support.(P12) My husband changed their thoughts about me. My husband's continual abuse and aggression after I was diagnosed with type 2 diabetes.(P9, P15)

Financial support from family members

The seven individuals said that their families provided financial support and helped them buy necessities such as medicine.

Quotes: “My older brother is always there to support me financially; he pays all of my medical costs.(P1,P3). My son has previously fulfilled all of my financial necessities. (P2, P13, P19, P20) and "He bought medicine with his money; all were paid for by my son.” (P16).

Emotional Motivational Support from Family

Acknowledging and praising victories, such as maintaining a normal blood sugar level or following a healthy diet, can boost motivation. Expressing words of encouragement at tough times strengthens the belief that progress is possible.

Quotes from patients: “Four Patient (P8,P12,P14,P18) stated that family members engage in fitness regimens or meal preparation, making healthy living a family commitment.” Three patients made the following unfavorable comment on the family's support: "My family member not support me, always shouting on me that I'm wrong always. It could incite anger

to be suggested that I am solely to blame for disease." Monitoring blood sugar levels or food intake feel stressful.”(P16 and P 8). “My daughter-in-law. Withdrawing emotional assistance at stressful times might make me feel alone and unsupported.” (P10)

Discussion

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic condition that requires years of therapy [29]. The standard of treatment for diabetes mellitus patients comprises food, exercise, medication, and glycemic control [30,31]. Previous study has shown that it is difficult for patients to undergo such therapy, thus they require aid from a variety of sources, one of which is their family. [31-35]. Patients who have family support will be more likely to comply with their home care [36,37]. Patients having diabetes mellitus who receive emotional and behavioral support from their relatives report feeling better[38]. Each family possesses a different approach for managing health issues in the family, both in regard to the health of particular family members and the overall health of the family group. The family process can have a significant influence on the family's overall health [39]. This study emphasizes the importance of family support for individuals with type 2 diabetes in terms of improved health status. In first theme, the participants' perceptions on the function and role of the family after the participants were diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus. The involvement of family in daily life routines significantly enhances the management of chronic conditions in type 2 diabetes. Their support can lead to improved health outcomes, emotional well-being, and a better overall quality of life for individuals managing type 2 diabetes. The analysis of the second theme was that the participants after being diagnosed with diabetes, the participants needed medication i.e. Family members assist them with organizing prescriptions using pills/tablets or medication schedules. These specific duties and roles are connected to the family's responsibility for providing medications as

well as the appearance of the sick role of participants who require therapeutic support from the family.

The third theme found was the participants' perceptions on the support they received from their families in terms of Help in diet management. Family support in the form of nutrition, emotional care, particularly for individuals with chronic conditions like diabetes mellitus, can develop into a family culture, while some women with type 2 diabetes do not receive assistance from their husbands. This study shows that men and women react differently to their spouse's medical problems. As a result, self-care behaviors such as dietary management are eventually developed. Most of the participants responded positively about their family support. Older persons were happy and grateful to receive the family support i.e. support from brother, son/daughter and spouse.

Self Monitoring the blood glucose, in this theme we have observed the patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus are prepared themselves to fight against the T2DM with the help of family support and motivation. Beyond this the work of wives to their husband in regards with the diet, medication and motivation were recorded and was very positive effect on the quality of life of male patients diagnosed with T2DM. We observed some of the negative points while this study, three of the female participants mentioned that their husbands didn't provide them much assistance. The seven individuals said that their families provided financial support and helped them buy necessities such as medicine. Acknowledging and praising victories, such as maintaining a normal blood sugar level or following a healthy diet, can boost motivation, emotional motivation from family member were seen in our study.

Conclusion:

Effective diabetic self-care requires patient education and motivation. Participants lacks knowledge of about food planning, regular physical activity, blood sugar monitoring. Furthermore, the replies in this study were

entirely self-reported. If patients thought that interviewers expected them to adhere to self-care activities at a high level, social desirability might have affected their replies, and the participants may have over-reported the prevalence of self-care practices. Finally, this was a cross-sectional research done just in one region in Pettah. We observed differences in self-care behaviors and family support among individuals with type 2 diabetes. Our study's personalized questions can inform health promotion efforts in the region and serve as a model for future research in low and middle-income countries. This study did not assess the efficacy of patient family support. It is advised that a research be conducted to assess the effectiveness of family support for patients.

Abbreviations

DM: diabetes mellitus

T2DM: Type 2 diabetes mellitus

P = Patient

FMs: Family Members

Data availability statement

The datasets used and analyzed during the current study will be made available by the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Acknowledgement

We are grateful to all the study participants and members of their family.

Funding sources: None

Authors' contributions

Each author contributed equally to this study and to the writing of the article. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Conflict of interest: None declared.

References

1. Goyal, R., Jialal, I., & Castano, M. (2022). Diabetes mellitus type 2 (nursing). StatPearls. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK568737/>

2. 1. Laranjo L, Neves AL, Costa A, Ribeiro RT, Couto L, Sá AB. Facilitators, barriers and expectations in the self-management of type 2 diabetes a qualitative study from Portugal. *Eur J Gen Pract.* (2015) 21:103–10. doi: 10.3109/13814788.2014.1000855
3. 2. Wu Y, Ding Y, Tanaka Y, Zhang W. Risk factors contributing to type 2 diabetes and recent advances in the treatment and prevention. *Int J Med Sci.* (2014) 11:1185. doi: 10.7150/ijms.10001
4. International Diabetes Federation. *IDF Diabetes Atlas*. Brussels, Belgium: International Diabetes Federation; 2015.
5. Norris S, Lau J, Smith S, Schmid C, Engelgau M. Self-management education for adults with type 2 diabetes: a meta-analysis of the effect on glycemic control. *Diabetes Care* 2002 Jul;25(7):1159-1171.
6. Deakin T, McShane CE, Cade JE, Williams RD. Group based training for self-management strategies in people with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* 2005 Apr 18(2):CD003417.
7. Powers MA, Bardsley J, Cypress M, Duker P, Funnell MM, Fischl AH, et al. Diabetes self-management education and support in type 2 diabetes: a joint position statement of the American Diabetes Association, the American Association of Diabetes Educators, and the Academy of Nutrition and Dietetics. *Clin Diabetes* 2016 Apr;34(2):70-80
8. 2. Kovacs Burns K, Nicolucci A, Holt RI, et al. Diabetes attitudes, wishes and needs second study (dawn2): cross-national benchmarking indicators for family members living with people with diabetes. *Diabet Med.* 2013;30:778–88.
9. 3. Bennich BB, Røder ME, Overgaard D, Egerod I, Munch L, Knop FK, et al. Supportive and non-supportive interactions in families with a type 2 diabetes patient: an integrative review. *DiabetolMetabSyndr.* 2017;9(57):1–9. [https:// doi. org/ 10. 1186/ s13098- 017- 0256-7](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13098-017-0256-7).
10. 4. Pesantes MA, Del Valle A, Diez-Canseco F, Bernabé-Ortiz A, Portocarrero J, Trujillo A, et al. Family support and diabetes: patient's experiences from a public hospital in Peru. *Qual Health Res.* 2018 Oct;28(12):1871–82. [https:// doi. org/ 10. 1177/ 10497 32318 784906](https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732318784906).
11. 5. Vongmany J, Luckett T, Lam L, Phillips J. Family behaviors that have an impact on the self-management activities of adults living with Type 2 diabetes: a systematic review and meta synthesis. *Diabet Med.* 2018;35:184–94. [https:// doi. org/ 10. 1111/ dme. 13547](https://doi.org/10.1111/dme.13547).
12. 7. Mayberry LS, Osborn CY. Family involvement is helpful and harmful to patients' self-care and glycemic control. *Patient Educ Couns.* 2014;97(3):418–25.
13. 11. Mayberry LS, Osborn CY. Family support, medication adherence, and glycemic control among adults with type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Care.* 2012;35(6):1239–45. [https:// doi. org/ 10. 2337/ dc11- 2103](https://doi.org/10.2337/dc11-2103).
14. 17. Black S, Maitland C, Hilbers J, Orinuela K. Diabetes literacy and informal social support: A qualitative study of patients at a diabetes centre. *J Clin Nurs.* 2016;26:248–57.
15. 4. Gehlawat M, Naik BN, Lakshminarayanan S, Kar SS. Dietary practices and barriers to dietary modification among diabetics and hypertensives in a rural health service area of Puducherry: a qualitative study. *Int J Health Allied Sci.*(2018) 7:139–44. doi: 10.4103/ijhas.IJHAS_158_17
16. 5. Shrivastava SR, Shrivastava PS, Ramasamy J. Role of self-care in management of diabetes mellitus. *J Diabetes Metab Disord.* (2013) 12:14. doi: 10.1186/2251-6581-12-14
17. 6. Fransen MP, Beune EJ, Baim-Lance AM, Bruessing RC, Essink-Bot ML. Diabetes self-management support for patients with low health literacy: Perceptions of patients and providers 针对低健康素养患者的

- 糖尿病自我管理支持: 患者与提供者的观念. *J Diabetes*. (2015) 7:418–25. doi: 10.1111/1753-0407.12191
18. 7. Winston RA, Shaya FT, Pradel FG, Laird A, Saunders E. Barriers to self-management of diabetes: a qualitative study among low-income minority diabetics. *Ethn Dis*. (2011) 21:27–32.
 19. 8. Byers D, Garth K, Manley D, Chlebogy D. Facilitators and barriers to type 2 diabetes self-management among rural African American adults. *J Health Dispar Res Pract*. (2016) 9:9.
 20. 9. Bukhsh A, Khan TM, Nawaz MS, Ahmed HS, Chan KG, Lee L-H, et al. Association of diabetes-related self-care activities with glycemic control of patients with type 2 diabetes in Pakistan. *Patient Prefer Adherence*. (2018) 12:2377. doi: 10.2147/PPA.S177314
 21. 10. Sarayani A, Jahangard-Rafsanjani Z, Hadjibabaie M, Ahmadvand A, Javadi M, Gholami K. A comprehensive review of adherence to diabetes and cardiovascular medications in Iran; implications for practice and research. *J Diabetes Metab Disord*. (2013) 12:57. doi: 10.1186/2251-6581-12-57
 22. 11. Coyle ME, Francis K, Chapman Y. Self-management activities in diabetes care: a systematic review. *Aust Health Rev*. (2013) 37:513–22. doi: 10.1071/AH13060
 23. 25. Mason M, editor. Sample size and saturation in PhD studies using qualitative interviews. *Forum Qual Sozialforschung*. (2010) 11:8.
 24. 11. Ulin P, Robinson E, Tolley E (2005). *Qualitative Methods in Public Health: A Field Guide for Applied Research*. San Francisco, Calif: Jossey-Bass.
 25. 32. Graneheim UH, Lundman B. Qualitative content analysis in nursing research: concepts, procedures and measures to achieve trustworthiness. *Nurse Educ Today*. (2004) 24:105–12. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2003.10.001
 26. 33. Elo S, Kyngäs H. The qualitative content analysis process. *J Adv Nurs*. (2008) 62:107–15. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2648.2007.04569.x
 27. 34. Green J, Thorogood N. *Qualitative Methods for Health Research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage (2018).
 28. 35. Braun V, Clarke V. Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qual Res Psychol*. (2006) 3:77–101. doi: 10.1191/1478088706qp063oa
 29. 3. Smeltzer SC, Bare BG, Hinkle JL, Kerry HC, Garret TM. *Brunner and Suddarth's Text Book of Medical Surgical Nursing*. Brunner LS. Brunner & Suddarth's textbook of medical-surgical nursing. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins; 2010. p. 151-7.
 30. 24. International Diabetes Federation. *IDF Diabetes Atlas*. 8th ed. International Diabetes Federation; 2017.25. American Diabetes Association. 2. Classification and diagnosis of diabetes: Standards of medical care in diabetes-2018. *Diabetes Care*. 2018;41(1):13-27. <https://doi.org/10.2337/dc19-s002> PMID:29222373
 31. 26. Al-Khawaldeh OA, Al-Hassan MA, Froelicher ES. Self-efficacy, self-management, and glycemic control in adults with Type 2 diabetes mellitus. *J Diabetes Complications*. 2012;26(1):10-6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdiacomp.2011.11.002> PMID:2222648427.
 32. 27 Ahola AJ, Groop PH. Barriers to self-management of diabetes. *Diabet Med*. 2013;30(4):413-20. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dme.12105> PMID:2327834228.
 33. 28 Baek RN, Tanenbaum ML, Gonzalez JS. Diabetes burden and diabetes distress: The buffering effect of social support. *Ann Behav Med*. 2014;48(2):145-55. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12160-013-9585-4> PMID:2455007229.
 34. 29 Simon-Tuval T, Shmueli A, Harman-Boehm I. Adherence to self-care behaviors among patients with Type 2

- diabetes-the role of risk preferences. *Value Health*. 2016;19(6):844-51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jval.2016.04.003> PMID:2771271330.
35. 30Mostafavi-Darani F, Zamani-Alavijeh F, Mahaki B, Salahshouri A. Exploring the barriers of adherence to dietary recommendations among patients with Type 2 diabetes: A qualitative study in Iran. *Nurs Open*. 2020;7(6):1735-45. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nop2.558> PMID:33072357
36. 10. Mansyur CL, Rustveld LO, Nash SG, Jibaja-Weiss ML. Social factors and barriers to self-care adherence in Hispanic men and women with diabetes. *Patient Educ Couns*. 2015;98(6):805-10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2015.03.001> PMID:25819551
37. 31. Mayberry LS, Harper KJ, Osborn CY. Family behaviors and Type 2 diabetes: What to target and how to address in interventions for adults with low socioeconomic status. *Chronic Illn*. 2016;12(3):199-215. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1742395316644303> PMID:27099387
38. 34. Kanbara S, Taniguchi H, Sakaue M, Wang DH, Takaki J, Yajima Y, et al. Social support, self-efficacy and psychological stress responses among outpatients with diabetes in Yogyakarta, Indonesia. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract*. 2008;80(1):56-62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.diabres.2007.12.015> PMID:1826230535.
39. 35Kaakinen JR, Coehlo DP, Gedaly-Duff V, Hanson SM, Kaakinen JR, Gedaly-Duff V, et al. *Family Health Care Nursing: Theory, Practice, and Research*. 4th ed., Vol. 74. Philadelphia, PA: Public Health, F.A Davis Company; 2010. p. 53-55.<https://doi.org/10.1177/1074840710383274>